
Strengthening The Independence of The King Saguna Jaya Sea Shell Artisan Group in Increasing Production Towards Export Markets in Serangan Village, South Denpasar District

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ABSTRACT: Especially handicrafts in Bali Province are experiencing very rapid development. The developments in question include dynamic forms, interests and production. Crafts from the island of the gods have a uniqueness in the form that can be seen from their very diverse types and reflect the culture and society of the island of Bali. In addition, the handicraft industry on the island of Bali is not only produced by established businesses, but also household-scale craftsmen who produce products with excellent quality. Along with the development of social media, resulting in the increasing popularity of Balinese craftsmen, this triggered an increase in handicraft orders from all over the world. One of the unique things is handicrafts in the form of handicrafts made from sea shells produced by craftsmen in Serangan Village There are several sea shell craft business groups in the Serangan area, one of which is a self-help business group initiated by I Made Kanan Jaya under the name King Saguna. The King Saguna group is a target group for PKM activities consisting of 13 shellfish artisans. This craft utilizes seashells including shell powder to become a craft that is worth selling. The raw materials for making them use local materials by buying from the public or fishermen. Not only environmentally friendly, but it can also help the economy of the surrounding community. Based on the results of observations of shellfish artisan partners, there are several problems that hinder partners in developing their businesses, including a lack of understanding of production input and output management, very limited production support facilities, lack of understanding to export, where craftsmen are constrained by information and access to start the export process; and lack of understanding of adequate bookkeeping. The purpose of the implementation of this partnership program is to support the increase in production and increase interest towards the export market., artisan groups are starting to be able to prepare the necessary documents for the prerequisites for permission to ship abroad if at any time is needed as well as study market trends through social media. There are three activities carried out in the community partnership program, namely mentoring and training for independent management of production inputs and outputs, and socialization of procedures for exporting. Counseling and training on bookkeeping The results of the program implementation show that after mentoring and socialization activities, partners are able to carry out financial recording to be more structured, thereby reducing errors during the financial recording process, increasing understanding of business management from the production side, as well as the desire to increase sales towards the international/export market.

KEYWORDS: sea shell crafts, production management, export market, bookkeeping

INTRODUCTION

The creative industry is one of Indonesia's leading sectors that supports exports. One of the regions that is consistent and strong in producing quality creative products is the Province of Bali. Many of the handicrafts produced in the Province of Bali are of good quality such as paintings, crafts made of metal, wood and sea shells. Especially handicrafts in Bali Province are experiencing very rapid development. The development in question includes dynamic forms, interests and production. In addition, the handicraft industry on the island of Bali is not only produced by established businesses, but also household-scale craftsmen who produce products with excellent quality. Most of the shell craft producers in Bali Province are small-scale industrial producers and are among the seventeen types of household-scale craft products that have penetrated the export market. (Pratama and Bendesa, 2015). Along with the development of social media, resulting in the increasing popularity of Balinese craftsmen, this triggered an increase in craft orders from all over the world. This opportunity has great potential to be developed, considering the export value of the handicraft industry which will continue to increase. In this situation, every country in the world transacts goods and services in terms of international trade (Bustami & Hidayat, 2013). International trade is a financial and business activity by establishing cooperation in the fields of export and import (Ladolo et al., 2022).

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Data from the Bali Provincial Trade and Industry Office states that Bali's handicraft export commodities consist of 17 types. Starting from musical instrument crafts, weaving, wood crafts to bone crafts. Among the 17 types, the export of wood crafts with the largest export value is 15.8 million dollars (IDR 241.6 billion), followed by shell crafts with 5.8 million dollars (IDR 89.6 billion) and silver crafts with 2.6 million dollars (IDR 4.0 billion). The use of seashells will generate a fairly high value for money if handled properly and also help preserve nature (Premasudha et al., 2017).

The Serangan Island area provides productive natural resources such as coral reefs, seagrass, mangrove forests and beaches. Marine wealth that is commonly used for making crafts that can be modified in the form of sea shells. The selection of sea shells as raw materials for making handicrafts is based on the lack of use of sea shells. In addition, the basis for choosing sea shells as accessories in the form of handicrafts is because the price of sea shells is relatively cheap. The use of sea shells, if pursued seriously, will bring promising results to increase the growth of the surrounding economy. Serangan Village, South Denpasar District is famous for producing shellfish crafts. Crafts that use shellfish waste materials are not prohibited items, in contrast to shellfish crafts that use shellfish that are still productive, are not allowed.

The production of shellfish handicrafts in Serangan Village, in addition to being able to meet the local and domestic markets, has also been sent to several countries and has even been educated to invite foreign tourists to learn to know and make various shellfish crafts so that this one commodity is increasingly going international. There are several sea shell craft business groups in the Serangan area, one of which is a self-help business group initiated by I Made Kanan Jaya under the name King Saguna The King Saguna group is a group consisting of 13 shell craftsmen. The King Saguna Jaya Shell Artisan Group led by Mr. I Made Kanan Jaya is one of the business groups that make sea shell crafts located in the southern Bali area, precisely in Serangan Village, South Denpasar District.

This handicraft business made from sea shells began in 2007 on the initiative of Mr. I Made Kanan Jaya himself. The idea to choose sea shells as raw materials to make crafts is because he believes that as long as he still has mangroves and beaches, sea shells will not run out. In addition, the use of sea shells as a craft is very environmentally friendly. This craft utilizes seashells including shell powder to become a craft that is worth selling. The raw materials for making them use local materials by buying from the public or fishermen. Not only environmentally friendly, but it can also help the economy of the surrounding community. The use of natural basic ingredients other than the main ingredients of shellfish that do not damage the environment is an illustration of how Mr. Made Kanan Jaya as the leader of the business group is very concerned about the environment where his business runs and directly implements the concept of Green Economy. From the business run by Mr. I Made Kanan Jaya, the crafts produced are diverse, including hair ties, bokor, fruit holders, necklaces, brooches, to turtles. During the handicraft business, Mr. I Made Kanan Jaya was able to reap a turnover of Rp 15,000,000 per month.

The King Saguna shellfish handicraft business group was formed with the spirit to support each other in producing shellfish handicrafts, helping each other through borrowing materials and production equipment that will later be replaced with the same goods and sharing and exchanging information, providing information on orders and sales of raw materials. This group of partners actively conducts meetings with fellow members. The purpose of this independent business group was established to improve the economy of fellow young craftsmen, empower their potential and take advantage of the economic potential of the export of shellfish handicrafts which will continue to increase in the future. MSMEs are trading businesses managed by individuals or business entities that refer to productive economic enterprises in accordance with the criteria set out in Law Number 8 of 2008. Meanwhile, MSMEs have also proven to be able to survive various shocks of the economic crisis. This makes strengthening the MSME group very necessary (Santoso et al., 2022, Setini, 2022).

The most basic problem for SMEs is the low productivity of SMEs. The biggest challenge for the creative industry is the declining market share and hampered production productivity. Based on the results of the observations that have been made, there are several problems faced by the non-help group of household-scale sea shell artisans in Serangan Village, namely that the management of this business has not been carried out properly, in the sense that it is still carried out conventionally. Based on the results of field visits and interviews, it can be concluded that business management is still managed in a simple way and is only routine. The preparation of financial statements that follow the standard rules of financial statements has not been carried out. The company's condition and financial performance can be reflected in the results of the presentation of the Financial Statements (Mustika and Aula, 2024). Financial books are not yet owned so that craftsmen do not know accurately the amount of profits obtained and the amount of costs spent in the production and operational processes. The problem that often occurs today, business actors prefer conventional methods even though they already know that technology can make business more efficient. (Martadiani et al., 2021).

Community service with this community partnership program scheme is research-based community service. Empirically, this condition is supported by the results of research by Maseko (2019) entitled "Accounting Practises of SMES in Zimbabwe: An Investigative Study of Record Keeping for Performance Measurement" stating that 50% of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises do not keep complete accounting records due to lack of accounting knowledge and the use of accounting information so that it cannot be measured business financial performance.

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The same finding was also found by Kwabena (2019), in its research entitled "Accounting Practices of SMES: A Case Study of Kumasi Metropolis in Ghana" succeeded in revealing that 60% of MSMEs have difficulties in accessing finance from financial institutions because these MSMEs do not have proper financial records. Therefore, it is recommended for MSMEs to create and keep detailed accounting records. So that it produces the right financial reports and can increase the accessibility of MSMEs to microfinance institutions Based on the results of observations of SME partners, shellfish artisans have several problems that hinder partners in developing their businesses. The problems are as follows: (1) Lack of understanding of the management of production inputs and outputs so that it affects the amount produced, (2) Lack of understanding from the group of shellfish artisans to export, where as long as the artisans are constrained by information and access to start the process of exporting, (3) Lack of understanding of adequate bookkeeping, where so far financial recording by the group of shellfish artisans is still using conventional methods Therefore, the PKM team aims to assist business actors in order to overcome the problems they face. More specifically, the purpose of this activity is to provide assistance and training for independent management of production inputs and outputs, socialization of procedures for exporting and counseling and bookkeeping training. The following are some of the product displays produced by the King Saguna Jaya shellfish artisan group

Figure 1. The production of the King Saguna Jaya sea shell artisan group

Based on the problems faced by SME partners, it is necessary to hold community service activities with partners of the King Saguna Jaya sea shell artisan group in Serangan Village. The purpose of service is to improve the ability of partners in business independence in increasing production towards the export market. This service is in accordance with the Strategic Plan of the DPPM of Warmadewa University, namely in the field of tourism development through a local economic approach.

METHOD

The location of this community service is in Serangan village, South Denpasar district, Bali. The form of implementation is focused on the partners of the King Saguna Jaya Sea Shell artisan group. The methods used are observation methods, interviews, counseling methods and providing assistance.

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1. Observation and interview methods.

Before this community service program is implemented, in-depth observations and interviews are first carried out with partners to identify the problems experienced by partners, set problem priorities, and discuss the right solutions to overcome these problems. The use of this method is expected to be able to recognize the problems of partners appropriately in accordance with business needs and capabilities of partners, as well as fostering the role of partners in designing, implementing, and accounting for the programs provided. These two methods are carried out continuously so that they can identify problems that are priorities to be handled.

2. Lecture / Extension method. The counseling method used to increase the independence of the community is carried out well by giving; counseling for independent management of production inputs and outputs, lectures/counseling on procedures for exporting. In this activity, the treatment carried out is socialization which aims to help increase the knowledge of partners in seeing export opportunities and understanding in the application of various stages towards export. Finally, the lecturer team explained the importance of bookkeeping in running a business. In this program, the team looks at the transaction history of partners and uses the data as the basis for bookkeeping training.

3. Mentoring method

The mentoring method is used in implementing the accounting system. Accounting systems can increase efficiency and be more effective in planning profits. Recording assistance in accordance with SAK, assistance in making product catalogs for export preparation and assistance and training for independent management of production inputs and outputs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the three priority problems that are handled with partners, the stages of steps taken to provide solutions to specific problems can be described as follows. The first step presented in Figure 2 is assistance in recording in accordance with the accounting system. Business actors are given books that have been formatted according to their needs. The goal is to make it easier to calculate the cost of goods, plan profits.

Figure 2 Assistance in Compiling Bookkeeping

The second step presented in Figure 3 is to conduct a lecture / counseling on how to export. In this activity, the treatment carried out is socialization which aims to help increase the knowledge of partners in seeing export opportunities and understanding in the application of various stages towards export. To export goods abroad, several special documents are required that include business legality and export documents.

The business legality documents are such as SIUP, TDP (Company Registration Certificate), NPWP, and NIK (Customs Identity Number). Meanwhile, export documents include invoices and packing lists that contain information about the contents of the package, such as the quantity, type, and weight of the goods.

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Figure 3. Counseling on export procedures

Activities in production inputs are closely related to the procurement of raw materials as the main materials for production activities. Components in production inputs generally consist of: raw materials and supporting materials, labor, capital, technology, market demand, business licensing and R&D (Research and Development). The process of procurement of raw materials and supporting materials for production activities is carried out individually/individually by business actors. In this case, there has not been collectivity in the procurement of raw materials, this is because the location of raw material resources is not far from SMEs so that business actors can obtain raw materials easily without incurring additional costs for transportation for raw material procurement. The material presented was counseling on how to choose a combination of input use to produce output with high productivity and efficiency. how to determine the optimal output level for a given level of input usage. 3. How to choose the right technology according to the company's conditions.

Figure 4. Counseling on independent management of production inputs and outputs

The third step in Figure 5. is product catalog making training Through product catalogs as a promotional medium both online and offline, it is expected to be able to increase sales and market share of sea shell crafts. On this occasion, partners were given the opportunity to submit complaints and obstacles faced. The problem of unfair competition can be overcome if business actors are able to provide products according to customer needs. Business actors must be proactive in seeking information so that they are able to innovate

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Figure 5. Product Catalog of King Saguna Jaya Sea Shell Artisan Group

The last step in Figure 6. The assistance of this electric saw/grinder is expected to be able to increase production capacity and product innovation so that it can increase product sales

Figure 6. Delivery of Capital Goods Equipment

The purpose of the Community Partnership Program activity is to increase business management independence and increase production towards the export market of the King Saguna Jaya sea shell artisan group. The social impact is to increase the existence of the role of MSMEs that produce shellfish crafts in supporting Bali as a tourist destination. The economic impact is expected to improve the welfare of MSME actors, and the community. The PKM team also donated equipment in the form of electric saw capital goods in accordance with the needs of partners to increase production capacity and product innovation. PKM Program activities are carried out with the support of all partners consisting of the King Saguna Jaya sea shell artisan group and the contribution of partners in PKM activities are presented in Table 1 as follows:

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Table 1 Benefits and contributions of partners in activities

Solutions offered	Benefit	Partner Contributions
Assistance in compiling books with an accounting system	Partners of the group of sea shell artisans are able to calculate the cost of goods in the correct way, have the correct bookkeeping so that they can plan profits	Partners are willing to be accompanied for 2 months which are monitored at the end of each month.
Counseling on production management and export socialization	Partners are able to carry out better business management. Namely (1) partners already have knowledge in managing production inputs and outputs, (2) partners are able to see export opportunities and understand the implementation of various stages towards exports	Partners provide a place, help with preparation, serve consumption and follow lectures with enthusiasm.
Assistance in the field of product catalog creation	Partners are able to create product catalogs as promotional media both online and offline so that they are able to increase sales	Partners prepare all equipment and, participants follow enthusiastically.

Based on the results of observations, this sea shell craft business has the opportunity to be developed with the development of tourism and culture. Sea shellfish business actors must start by implementing a product innovation strategy. Sea shell products can be developed in terms of materials, shapes, colors and designs In terms of materials, innovations are made with dried banana leaves/claras so that they can utilize waste The next strategy is to implement a recording system using an accounting system. Recording with the right method in every transaction makes it easier for business actors to determine prices and plan profits. To market products, use marketing strategies through online media with the latest product catalogs Steps to develop a sea shell business can be done through strategies that are tailored to both management and financial capabilities.

CONCLUSION

Community service activities through training and mentoring activities have a positive impact on sea shell craft business actors. Assistance activities in compiling books with an accounting system are useful in determining the correct cost of goods. Entrepreneurs have the ability to make correct records in accordance with the accounting system about the business they are running. Correct bookkeeping is also useful as a requirement to apply for credit at a time when they need additional capital. Community service activities have the goal of supporting increased production and increasing interest in the export market. Through empowerment and collaboration programs, this activity has succeeded in producing a positive impact in developing the sea shell craft industry and helping to encourage economic growth at the local level. This empowerment activity also strengthens the King Saguna Jaya seashell artisan group. Through training and mentoring, partners gain new knowledge that supports the quality of work and innovation in their products. Overall, the empowerment activities of the sea shell artisan group in Serangan Village have been successful in supporting the strengthening of the independence of sea shell craft business actors. These measures not only benefit the artisans individually, but also contribute to the development of the local economy and the preservation of valuable cultural heritage.

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